

Chemical Examination of *Cuscuta Reflexa*, Roxb. Part I. The Constituents.

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Cuscuta reflexa (Roxb.) known as Amarvel or Akashbel in Hindusthani and Swarnalata in Bengali, is a common golden yellow dodder like parasite belonging to the Natural Order *Convolvulaceae*. It is common throughout India growing on thorny or other shrubs.

As regards its medicinal properties Mahomedan writers consider it to be alterative and depurative, a purge for bile and black bile, useful in affections of the brain such as fits, melancholy, insanity, etc. (Dymock, "Pharmacographica Indica," 1890, Vol. II, 548). It is also supposed to be purgative and used externally against itch, and internally in protracted fevers, retention of wind, and induration of the liver (Kirtikar and Basu, "Indian Medicinal Plants," 1918, Vol. II, 888).

Very little is known regarding the chemical composition of *Cuscuta reflexa*, though Barbey in 1895 (*J. Pharm.*, 1895, vi, 2, 107) working on another variety of cuscute, namely, *C. epithimum*, isolated from it an yellow amorphous colouring matter by precipitation of an alkaline extract with dilute sulphuric acid and subsequent extraction of the precipitate with ether. He termed the colouring principle cuscutin but gave no analytical data. He also isolated along with tannins and resinous substances a small amount of a crystalline substance having a faint odour of coumarin.

On account of the medicinal properties associated with *Cuscuta reflexa* in India the present authors were tempted to put it to a more systematic chemical analysis. We have been able to isolate cuscutin, the colouring matter of Barbey (*loc. cit.*), in a crystalline form (0.2 %) along with a white crystalline substance having the properties of a lactone, called by us cuscotalin (1.0 %), a small amount of brown wax (0.1 %) and large quantities of reducing sugars.

For the isolation of cuscutin we tried at first the method adopted by Barbey, but the colouring matter obtained was non-fusible and could not be made to crystallise. We, therefore, worked with sun-dried material and got the colouring matter in a crystalline form from the aqueous solution of the alcoholic extract after the removal of cuscotalin.

Cuscutin is feebly acidic in properties since it dissolves in sodium bicarbonate solution with slight effervescence and can be precipitated

unchanged by acids. It forms a diacetyl, a dicarbethoxy and a dimethoxy derivative and gives a very delicate violet green colour with ferric chloride; hence it contains two phenolic hydroxy groups. It does not form any oxime.

Cuscutalin is a lactone. It dissolves in caustic alkalis with a yellow colour. Although containing no aldehydic or ketonic group it reduces Tollen's reagent slowly and gives a reddish brown colouration with an alkaline solution of potassium nitroprusside. These reactions definitely prove it to be a member of the $\Delta\alpha\beta$ -lactones, which have been adequately reviewed by Jacobs (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1926, 67, 333; *Phys. Rev.*, 1933, 13, 222). More work on the elucidation of its constitution is in progress.

Pharmacologically cuscutalin appears to be a potent drug. It has been sent to King George's Medical College, Lucknow, where a detailed study of its physiological properties will be undertaken.

EXPERIMENTAL.

30 Kg. of the fresh *Cuscuta reflexa* were collected from the neighbourhood of Allahabad in the months of October and November from various host plants. A preliminary examination showed that the chemical composition of the parasitic plant was practically independent of the nature of its host. It was dried in the sun and by so doing lost about 90% of its moisture. It was then finely crushed and when burnt in a porcelain dish left 9.85 % of a brownish white ash. This ash consisted of 19.12 % of water-insoluble and 80.88 % of water-soluble inorganic material. The following elements and radicals were detected in the ash: Sodium, potassium, magnesium (traces), calcium, nitrates, phosphates, carbonates and silica.

Samples of the finely crushed material were extracted in a Soxhlet's apparatus using various solvents when the following amounts of extracts dried at 100°, were obtained.

Petroleum ether extract.—The extract was of a deep green colour, containing a greenish white crystalline matter suspended in it, yield 15.2%.

Chloroform extract.—The extract was of a pale yellow colour and contained a small amount of a pale yellow deposit, yield 18.0%.

Alcoholic extract.—The colour of the extract was greenish yellow containing a large amount of crystalline matter, yield 22.5%. It

reduced Fehling's solution easily. It gave a lead salt with neutral lead acetate, a silver salt with silver nitrate, deep greenish blue colour with ferric chloride. No reactions for alkaloids were obtained.

Aqueous extract.—The extract was of a light orange colour, reduced Fehling's solution readily and gave a deep green colour with ferric chloride, yield 5.0 %.

The powdered material (2.5 kg.) was extracted with boiling alcohol in a big extraction flask of 5 litre capacity, till the extract failed to give any white stuff on cooling. The extract, which was of a light yellow colour, was filtered hot and on cooling deposited cuscutalin which was filtered, washed with cold alcohol till a perfectly white stuff was obtained. In order to remove the whole of the crystalline matter from the plant at least five extractions are necessary. It was dried in *vacuo* over calcium chloride and weighed 25 g., m.p. 64°. It was recrystallised from methyl alcohol, when a yellowish brown substance was left which would not go into solution even on prolonged boiling and melted at 74°. From its properties it appears to be a wax. The quantity obtained was too small for any detailed investigation. Cuscutalin was finally recrystallised from a large volume of boiling ethyl alcohol, when perfectly white crystalline flakes were obtained, m.p. 68°.

Properties of cuscutalin.—Cuscutalin is a colourless crystalline substance, insoluble in water, soluble in benzene, phenol, chloroform, ether and slightly so in ethyl alcohol, methyl alcohol, ethyl acetate, pyridine and acetic acid. It dissolves in boiling caustic potash or caustic soda solution giving a beautiful yellow colouration. It decolourises a solution of bromine in chloroform and a dilute alkaline solution of potassium permanganate. It gives a positive Salkowski's reaction, *i.e.*, a solution of cuscutalin in chloroform and concentrated sulphuric acid gives a red and finally a green colouration. If cuscutalin is dissolved in chloroform and a little acetic anhydride is added followed by concentrated sulphuric acid a green colouration is obtained which finally changes to blue. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a yellow colour which finally changes to deep red on warming. With concentrated hydrochloric acid it gives no colouration, but with concentrated nitric acid a bright red colouration is developed on heating. It gives no precipitate with lead acetate or silver nitrate, but with alcoholic ferric chloride a light red colouration is produced. With Tollen's reagent a light yellow coloured solution is formed which slowly changes to brown

and finally a gradual reduction takes place. With alkaline solution of potassium nitroprusside it gives a reddish brown colouration. [Found: C, 74.0, 74.3; H, 3.5, 3.7; M.W. (cryoscopic in phenol) 260, 281. $C_{18}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 74.5; H 3.4 per cent. M.W. 290].

Isolation of cuscutin.—The combined alcoholic extract after the removal of cuscutalin was concentrated when a thick syrupy greenish red liquid was obtained, smelling of sugars. This was then extracted successively with benzene, ethyl acetate and water.

The benzene extract was deep green in colour and contained a large amount of chlorophyll. This was evaporated to dryness and the dried mass washed repeatedly with cold alcohol and crystallised from boiling alcohol when white flakes of cuscutalin (m.p. 67-68°) were obtained.

The ethyl acetate extract was golden red in appearance and on concentration became very syrupy. Nothing chemically definite could be isolated from it.

After treatment with benzene and ethyl acetate, the original mass was dissolved in ice-cold water with constant stirring. A brown stuff separated (m.p. 140°) which was filtered and washed. It was dissolved in a large quantity of water at the ordinary temperature and the golden yellow solution kept in an ice-chest overnight, when pale yellow crystals separated which were filtered, washed and dried, m.p. 208.9° (decomp.) with previous softening at 179°.

The aqueous extract after the removal of cuscutin as described above, was concentrated and was found to reduce Fehling's solution readily. It contained a large amount of reducing sugars.

Properties of cuscutin.—It is easily soluble in ethyl and methyl alcohols, pyridine and acetic acid, less so in acetone and water and insoluble in benzene, ethyl acetate, chloroform, ether and petroleum ether. The solution in all these solvents has an orange yellow colour. It decomposes if boiled with water. Cuscutin dissolves readily in solutions of alkali carbonates, bicarbonates and hydroxides giving a bright orange-yellow solution, which undergoes decomposition if boiled. It can, however, be precipitated from these solvents by the addition of dilute mineral acids. With concentrated sulphuric acid a reddish brown colouration is produced with a slight fluorescence; with concentrated nitric acid a blood-red colouration is developed which changes to light orange on warming. In concentrated hydrochloric acid it dissolves with an orange-yellow colouration. It produces a green precipitate with ferric chloride, and yellowish white

precipitate with lead acetate and a white precipitate with silver nitrate. The dilute alkaline solution decolourises a solution of potassium permanganate. It gave a negative test for flavones and was completely decolourised on being boiled with ammonia and zinc dust. It was not glucosidic in character. [Found: C, 53.4, 53.2; H, 3.9, 3.7; M.W. (cryoscopic in phenol) 330, 342, (lead salt) 338. $C_{15}H_{12}O_9$ requires C, 53.6; H, 3.6 per cent. M.W. 336).

Lead salt.—To 0.5 g. of cuscutin dissolved in alcohol, an alcoholic solution of lead acetate was added drop by drop till the yellow precipitate was no longer obtained. The lead salt was filtered, washed thoroughly and dried. It was a yellowish brown stuff. (Found: Pb, 48.07. $C_{30}H_{18}O_{18}Pb_3$ requires Pb, 48.2 per cent).

Diacetylcuscutin was prepared from 1 g. of cuscutin, 25 c.c. of acetic anhydride and a little fused sodium acetate by refluxing for 2 hours. It crystallised from glacial acetic acid as yellowish brown micro-crystalline needles, m.p. 140°. [Found: C, 54.1; H, 3.9. $C_{15}H_{10}O_9$ (C_2H_3O)₂ requires C, 54.4; H, 3.8 per cent].

Dicarbethoxycuscutin.—1 G. of cuscutin was dissolved in pyridine and an excess of ethyl chloroformate was slowly added with vigorous shaking till the solution had a slight pink colour. It was then poured into water, a black oil separated which solidified on keeping in water to a hard vitreous mass. It was filtered and crystallised from ethyl alcohol as brown crystalline flakes, m.p. 151° (decomp.). It dissolved in most organic solvents and gave no colouration with alkalis. [Found: C, 52.9; H, 3.9. $C_{15}H_{10}O_9$ ($C_6H_{10}O_4$) requires C, 52.5; H, 4.2 per cent].

Dimethoxycuscutin.—0.8 G. of cuscutin was dissolved in strong caustic potash and dimethyl sulphate added slowly with constant shaking. More alkali was then added and the mixture cooled in water and shaken vigorously for an hour, when an oily liquid separated which gradually solidified on keeping in cold water. It was filtered and crystallised from alcohol as pale yellow crystalline flakes, m.p. 193°. [Found: C, 55.8; H, 4.9. $C_{15}H_{10}O_7$ (OMe)₂ requires C, 56.0; H, 4.4 per cent).

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